

Quality of Life and Psychological Well-Being among Elderly Living in Old Age Homes and Living with their Families in Selected Areas of Uttarakhand

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ABSTRACT

Background of study: Ageing is a natural process and an inevitable one. Old age is a crucial phase where the physiological, psychological and socio-cultural changes in elderly affect their living pattern and their health status too in terms of psychological well-being and also affect their quality of life.

Objective of the study: Present study was conducted with objective to assess the quality of life and psychological well-being among elderly living in old age homes and living with their families in selected areas of Uttarakhand.

Material and Methods: A quantitative research approach with descriptive comparative design was used to assess the QOL (quality of life) and PWB (psychological well-being) among elderly living in old age homes and living with their families. The Population consisted of old people residing in selected old age homes and community area. The study was conducted at selected old age homes and community area of Uttarakhand. Purposive sampling technique was used to select the 164 subjects from the population i.e. 82 subjects from respective old age homes and 82 subjects from selected community area. Socio-demographic Proforma, WHO QOL-BREF scale and self-developed Psychological well-being scale was used to assess the QOL and PWB among elderly with the help of structured interview method.

Result: The result of the study shows that overall mean score of QOL for elderly living in old age homes and those living with their families was 68.47 and 97.43 respectively. Similarly overall mean score for PWB among elderly living in old age homes and those living with their families was 45.31 and 66.86 respectively which showed that QOL and PWB was good among those elderly who were living with their families as compare to old age homes inmates. On comparison of overall mean of QOL it was found that mean score for QOL with S.D for elderly living in old age homes and living with families was 68.47 ± 10.752 and 97.44 ± 8.564 similarly on comparison of overall mean score of PWB it was found that score was 45.32 ± 6.385 and 66.87 ± 5.86 which was found to be statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

Conclusion: Hence the overall findings suggest that quality of life and psychological well-being was good among elderly who were living with their families as compare to those who were living in old age homes.

KEYWORDS: Quality of life, Psychological well-being, Elderly, Old age homes, families

INTRODUCTION

Human life is an endless journey. We all human beings grow, develop and mature in our lives. As we continue to move on in our life, we move from one stage in life to the next stage of life.^[1] Ageing is that reality of human existence on this earth from which no individual can escape. The normal ageing process starts with biological aspects of ageing and also includes great psychological impact on life. In terms of biology ageing can be defined as consistent changes occurring in mature biologically living being existing under oppressive surroundings as they proceed in ordered age group. Further these consistent transformation give rise to physical and emotional changes in old age.^[1] This time right

now there are approximately around 75 million of people who are in age group of 60 years and above and it is predicted to rise to enormous population that is 180 million by the year 2025 (According to Registrar General of India 2006). As elderly are more prone to physical and psychological problems, the increasing number of old age people is frightening for the general public, community and country as a whole. ^[1] Elderly people in terms of various problems are more susceptible to mental diseases because of anatomical deterioration of brain structures, ailments linked with physical health, cerebral illness; social and economical factors such as disintegration of family aid help system and diminishing financial support.^[2] There has been steep incline

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in number of elderly in India. India is a nest for 77 million and second largest number of aged people in the world next to China. This terrific increase in the population of elderly directs our concern toward maintenance of their wellbeing.^[2] General welfare in terms of physical health of old age people is becoming even more suitable and appropriate with population drift which is occurring towards an aging community. In Indian society there is less understanding and recognition about unusual and exceptional needs and caretakers are still to comprehend the fundamentals of care of old age people i.e.(Physiological, emotional, societal, intellectual support).^[3] However there are studies which recognize and mention the importance for autonomy because of the reason for the old age people staying in old age homes. Lacking of care within the family, inadequate housing are considered as reason by many studies for older people to join in old age homes.^[4] Ageing, along with the functional decline in terms of physical and psychological disability, economic dependence, and social cut off, freedom of young generation, compromises QOL.^[4] At worldwide level, the welfare of elderly is an major field of interest reflecting health conditions and wellbeing of this endangered population.^[4] Numerous investigations have displayed that chronic gruesome states are linked with poor quality of life Thus the quality of life and general well-being among elderly is a significant and key area of interest reflecting the physical fitness and good welfare of this jeopardized populace. But there is shortage of studies directed towards assessing the QOL among elderly in India more so in old age homes hence current investigation was intended to highlight the QOL and Psychological well-being among elderly population as there is limited understanding of factors influencing their QOL and PWB.^[4]

In this context by lightening the above facts the current investigation was an effort by researcher for determining the QOL and PWB among old age population residing in old age homes and family setup in selected areas of Uttarakhand. Further the findings from this investigation will provide baseline details and particulars on the conditions of elderly in the community and will also help to facilitate the need for development of a policy framework for support, interventions and further research on elderly in India.^[4]

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study design, study population and sampling

A quantitative research approach with descriptive comparative design was used to assess the quality of life and Psychological well-being among elderly living in old age homes and living with families. The study population comprised of elderly living in selected old age homes and living with families in selected community area. Study was conducted at Geeta kutir Ashram (Haridwar) and Prem Dham (Dehradun) and Bullawala community area of Uttarakhand. Purposive sampling technique was used to select 164 subjects from population (82 each from old age homes and community area). Socio-demographic Proforma, WHOQOL-BREF scale and self -developed PWB scale was used to assess QOL and PWB among elderly. Formal Ethical permission was taken from Ethical committee for conducting the study. The study participants were interviewed after explaining academic nature of this research, and were assured that information collected from them would be kept confidential. Socio-demographic characteristics, quality of life and psychological well-being were assessed using structured interview method

RESULTS

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage distribution of elderly with their selected socio-demographic characteristics living in the old age homes and those living with their families.

N=164

Sr. No.	Demographic variables	Elderly(in old age homes) n=82		Elderly(in families) n=82	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
1	Age				
	a) 60-80 years	75	91.5	77	93.9
	b) 81-100 years	7	8.5	5	6.1
2	Gender				
	a) Male	45	54.9	49	59.8
	b) Female	37	45.1	33	40.2
3	Religion				
	a) Hindu	73	89.0	64	78
	b) Christian	9	11.0	0	0
	c) Sikh	0	0	18	22
4	Marital status				
	a) Married	8	9.8	61	74.4
	b) Unmarried	11	13.4	1	1.2
	c) Widow	27	32.9	13	15.9
	d) Widower	32	39.0	6	7.3
	e) Separated	4	4.9	0	0
	f) Divorcee	0	0	1	1.2
5	Educational qualification				
	a) Primary	32	39.0	50	61
	b) High school	26	31.7	16	19.5
	c) Intermediate	13	15.9	12	14.6
	d) Graduation and above	11	13.4	4	4.9

6	Retirement				
	a) Yes	19	23.2	19	23.2
	b) No	63	76.8	63	76.8
7	Source of income				
	a) Pension	32	39.0	62	75.6
	b) Other	50	61.0	20	24.4
8	Physical Illness				
	a) Yes	57	69.5	28	34.1
	b) No	25	30.5	54	65.0
9	Duration of living in old age home/families				
	a) 1-20years	80	97.6	68	82.9
	b) 21-40 years	2	2.4	11	13.4
	c) 41-60 years	0	0	3	3.7
10	Type of family in they lived/living				
	a) Joint	79	96.3	78	95.1
	b) Nuclear	03	3.7	4	4.9
11	No. of children with they lived/living				
	a) One	26	31.7	14	17.1
	b) More than 1	43	52.4	67	81.7
	c) No children	13	15.9	1	1.2

Table 2: Overall Mean, domain wise mean and mean% age of QOL (quality of life) among elderly living in old age homes and living with their families.

N=164

Variables	Quality of life among elderly living in old age homes.		Quality of life among elderly living with their families	
overall mean	68.48±10.752		97.44±8.564	
Quality of life domains	Domain wise mean± S.D	Mean Percentage	Domain wise mean± S.D	Mean Percentage
Domain1(Physical)	16.93±4.44	48.39	26.46±3.96	75.60
Domain2(Psychological)	15.31±2.85	51.05	21.21±2.75	70.73
Domain3 (Social relations)	5.90±1.95	39.34	11.25±0.86	75.03
Domain4(Environment)	24.71±2.84		30.79±2.18	
	Total domain mean= 62.85	61.79	Total domain mean=89.71	76.98

From table 2 it can be inferred that overall mean of QOL of elderly living in old age homes was 68.48±10.752. Further Domain wise mean in this table suggests that mean QOL score in domain 4(environmental) was higher i.e.(24.71±2.84) than other domains; whereas mean score in domain 3 i.e.(5.90±1.95) shows that social relationships were weak among subjects as compared to other domains.

Furthermore overall mean for QOL of elderly living with their families was 97.44±8.564. Further domain wise mean in this table suggests that mean QOL score in domain 4(environmental) was higher i.e. (30.79±2.18) than other domains; whereas mean score in domain 3(social relationship) i.e. (11.25±.86) shows that social relationships were weak among subjects as compared to other domains. Above findings indicate that quality of life among elderly who were living with their families was good as compare to elderly who were living in old age homes.

Table no.3: Overall Mean, domain wise mean and mean% age of PWB (Psychological well-being) among elderly living in old age homes and living with their families.

N=164

Variables	Psychological well-being among elderly living in old age homes.		Psychological well-being among elderly living with families	
overall mean	45.32±6.385		66.87±5.866	
Psychological well-being domains	Domain wise mean± S.D	Mean Percentage	Domain wise mean± S.D	Mean Percentage
Domain1(Physical)	12.41±2.44	38.86	17.80±2.41	55.28
Domain2(Psychological)	15.36±2.90	39.18	23.67±3.05	58.69
Domain3(Family relations)	11.65±2.36	35.47	16.58±1.24	50.87
Domain4(Environment)	5.87±0.88		8.80±0.81	
	Total domain mean=45.29	30.73	Total domain mean=66.85	47.34

Table no. 3 depicts that overall mean for PWB (Psychological well-being) among elderly living in old age homes was 45.32 ± 6.385 . Domain wise mean score in domain 2 (psychological health) i.e. (15.36 ± 2.90) was higher than the other domains; whereas low score of domain 4 (environmental) i.e. (5.87 ± 0.88) shows that inadequate environmental sanitation/conditions was affecting their psychological well-being. Similarly overall mean for PWB (Psychological well-being of elderly living with their families) was 66.87 ± 5.866 . Domain wise mean score in domain 2 (Psychological health) i.e. (23.67 ± 3.05) was higher than the other domains; whereas low score in domain 4 (environmental) i.e. (8.80 ± 0.81) shows that in appropriate environmental conditions was affecting the PWB of elderly who all were living with families. Findings above further shows that psychological well-being among elderly who were living with their families was higher in comparison to those who were living in old age homes.

Table no. 4: Comparison of mean of QOL (quality of life).

Mean±S.D		‘t’-value	p-value
Elderly living in old age homes	Elderly living with their families		
68.47±10.752	97.43±8.564	19.08	0.01

df=162,* Significant at 0.05 level of significance ($p \leq 0.05$)

Data presented in **table 4** represent that independent t-test was applied to compare the QOL among elderly living in old age homes and living with their families and comparison of mean of QOL among elderly was done for two groups, for elderly that were living in old age homes mean with S.D was (68.47 ± 10.752) and for elderly living with their families mean with S.D was (97.44 ± 8.564) with t-value of 19.08 at 0.01 level of significance which showed that there was highly statistically significant difference between two groups i.e. between elderly living in old age homes and those living with their families.

Table no.5: Comparison of mean of PWB (psychological well-being)

Mean±S.D		“t”-value	p-value
Elderly living in old age homes	Elderly living with their families		
45.32±6.385	66.87±5.86	22.506	0.01

df= 162,*Significant at 0.05 level of significance ($p \leq 0.05$)

Table no. 5 represents that comparison of overall mean of PWB was done between two groups that is between elderly living in old age homes and those living with their families. Mean score with S.D for elderly living in old age homes was 45.32 ± 6.385 and mean score with S.D for elderly living with their families was 66.87 ± 5.87 with t-value of 22.506 at 0.01 level of significance which showed that there was highly statistically significant difference between the two groups i.e. between elderly living in old age homes and those living with their families.

Fig. no. 1: Graph showing Percentage distribution of quality of life among elderly living in old age homes and living with their families.

Fig.no.2: Graph showing Percentage distribution of Psychological well-being among elderly living in old age homes and living with their families.

DISCUSSION

Summary of Findings:

Major findings of the study were:

For elderly people living in old age homes:

- Majority (91.5%) of elderly who were living in old age homes were in between age group of 60-80 years.
- More than half (54.9%) of elderly were male and most (89.0%) of elderly were Hindu whereas (11.0%) of elderly were Christian.
- Maximum (39.0%) of elderly were widower whereas (9.8%) were married, (13.4%) were unmarried, (32.9%) were widows, and (4.9%) of elderly were living separated from their spouse.
- Maximum (39.0%) of elderly were educated up to primary level whereas (31.7%) were educated up to high school, (15.9%) were educated up to intermediate & only (13.4%) of elderly had education up to graduation and above.
- Most (76.8%) of elderly were not retired from their job.
- Two third (61.0%) of elderly were having other source of income than pension.
- Most (69.5%) of elderly were suffering from physical/mental illness.
- Majority (97.6%) of elderly there duration of staying in old age homes was between 1-20 years.
- Majority (96.3%) of elderly lived in joint family before coming to old age homes.
- More than half (52.4%) of elderly in old age homes lived with their more than one children in their family and only (15.9%) of elderly were not having children.

For elderly people living with their families

- Majority (93.9%) of elderly who were living with their families, there age group was between 60-80 yrs.
- 'More than half' of i.e. (59.8%) of elder people were male.
- Most (78%) of elderly were Hindu and rest (22%) were Sikh.
- Most (74.4%) of elderly were married whereas (1.2%) of elderly were unmarried & rest (1.2%) were divorcee, (15.9%) of elderly were widow & (7.3%) were widower.

- Two third (61%) of elderly were educated up to primary level whereas (19.5%) of elderly were educated up to high school, (14.6%) of elderly were educated up to intermediate class & only (4.6%) were having education of graduation & above.
- Four fifth (76.8%) of elderly were not retired in families.
- Four fifth (75.6%) of elderly were having pension as there source of income.
- Most (65.9%) of elderly were not having any kind of physical/ mental illness.
- Majority (82.9%) of elderly were having duration of living with their family in between of 1-20 years.
- Majority (95.1%) of elderly were living in joint family.
- Majority (81.7%) of elderly were living with their more than one child.

DISCUSSION

Findings of the study revealed that on the basis of overall Mean \pm S.D and domain wise mean the quality of life among elderly living with their families was good as compare to elderly living in old age homes.

Similar findings were supported by Dr. S. Chandrika, Dr. P. Radhakumari, Dr. B. Madhavi (2015) who carried out an investigation on the quality of life of elder people residing in elderly homes and community in Vishakhapatnam city. The researchers concluded that the mean scores of quality of life in all four domains that is physical, psychological, social relations and environment were found to be better among elderly living in community than in old age homes.^[5]

Further findings also revealed that on the basis of overall Mean \pm S.D, domain wise mean, the psychological well-being among elderly living with their families was found to be higher as compare to elderly living in old age homes.

Similar findings were supported by Suprithy Paliwal, Neha Singh (2017) who carried out an investigation on psychological well-being among senior citizens from community and non-community living in which results showed that overall mean for elderly living in community

living was higher than mean of non-community area elders thus concluding that psychological well-being was better among elderly living in community areas than non-community areas.^[6]

On comparison of Mean of quality of life among elderly people living in old age homes and living with their families it was found that there was highly significant difference between the two groups.

Similar findings were supported by Nagesh Jamwal (2016) who carried out an investigation on psychosocial consequences among elderly living in institutional and non-institutional settings. The results of study concluded that on comparison of quality of life among elderly there was significant difference between institutionalized elderly and elderly living with their families on physical, psychological, social relationship domains.^[7]

On comparison of Mean of psychological well-being among elderly people living in old age homes and living with their families it was found that there was highly significant difference between two groups.

Similar findings were supported by Supriya Paliwal, Neha Singh where findings of study suggested that there was significant difference in Psychological well-being of senior citizens from community and non-community living.^[8]

Strength of the study:

Thus descriptive comparative design was used in the study for assessing the quality of life and psychological well-being among elderly and structured interview method was used for collecting the data thus better response was noted by interacting face to face from participants. Findings from this study was easily generalized as samples were representative of study population. The problems which elderly was facing in old age homes were also easily assessed with the help of interview method therefore in future with the help of this data, interventional study can be done on providing information about health in relation to activity and changes in physical surrounding and increase in societal relationship thus enhancing QOL and PWB of old age population.

Limitation of the study:

Thus it was a comparative study only therefore no interventions were given to participants and were not followed up again.

CONCLUSION

The present study revealed that quality of life and psychological well-being was good among elderly who were living with their families as compare to those elderly who were living in old age homes. Elderly in old age homes faced many problems particularly related to physical illness and

their altered social relationships and psychological aspect also affected their QOL whereas their altered physiological status, altered social relationship and altered environmental aspect affected their overall PWB. Further there is a scope to have a better understanding about factors behind poor psychological well-being and quality of life domains wise through qualitative research.

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Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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